

Decentralized Infrastructure of Micro-Credentials and Blockchain Technology

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Abstract

Higher education is being reshaped by technology and this ongoing change is seen in many layers of the educational environment. Yet the management of academic credentials hasn't been fully affected by the technology that is reshaping the learning preferences of the learners. For the last ten years, learners have started to fulfill their needs for learning via online sources which are supported by either universities or private companies. Upon completing an online certificate program, learners ask for valid certificates that are issued by reliable organizations. At this point, the idea of Micro-credentials (MCs) has emerged as MCs offer bite-sized and flexible online courses to learners according to their needs. Via some online learning platforms, learners have started to rethink their career paths to meet the requirements of the day. These credentialing ecosystems have grown in numbers over time and learners have felt the need for trust for the issuer bodies and the exchange of the given credits. To fulfill this need, Blockchain technologies can be used to decentralize the credentialing system. Blockchain technologies, if well-planned and used strategically, can provide some benefits for the credibility and authenticity of the MCs. These benefits include "timestamping" to ensure validity and "being permanent" to make transactions immutable. At this point, Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAO) could be a relatively new blockchain acronym that aims to decentralize the management of organizations with the help of smart contract which is the backbone technology of the DAOs. In this paper, the background knowledge on MC's and the possible benefits, and drawbacks of using Blockchain technologies in the decentralization of MCs are discussed. At the end of this study, some suggestions are given for future research.

Keywords: Micro-credentials, decentralized autonomous organizations, blockchain in education.

Introduction

It is undeniable that technology enriched learning environments will play an important role for the future of education. Changing living and working conditions of individuals and unexpected problems experienced by societies (such as the Corona virus, floods, and earthquakes) have played a major role in the transfer of individuals' learning processes to digital environments. Like many other sectors, today's education and training system has been largely disrupted – digitization, new technologies and changing learning needs pose great challenges, especially for the higher education sector (Resei et al., 2019).

In the 21st century, where the learning needs of the learners, the age range at which they continue their education and for what purpose they continue their education differ, learners have made their skills acquisition and development processes continuous with short-term courses within the framework of lifelong education. The OECD's Trends Shaping Education series, in a 2019 report that explores global megatrends affecting the future of education, explores how to promote lifelong learning alongside lifelong learning - the skills needed to thrive amid changing life and work patterns as the digital economy evolves and these underlined the need to be equipped with knowledge and attitudes (OECD, 2019). For years, open and distance learning environments supported by technology have made possible this needed community engagement and lifelong learning.

As the famous futurist Alvin Toffler said, "The illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn". The phrase underlined the continuity of learning, the necessity of forgetting outdated knowledge and the importance of re-acquisition of new knowledge to survive in the digital age. The observed exponential increase in the number of students enrolled in MOOCs can be considered as an indicator of people's continuing need for lifelong learning. According to the report published in Class Central by Dhawal Shah in 2018, the number of students enrolled in MOOCs was 101 million. While this number reached a sizable figure such as 180 million student enrollment in 2020 with the participation of 950 universities, this figure reached 220 million students in 2021 with the increase in the number of people who spend more time in front of the screen at home due to the Corona pandemic. One of the reasons why micro-credentials is preferred is that it provides a learning journey that is shaped especially in line with the needs of adult learners. Micro-credentials, which also provides the opportunity to continue higher education at more

reasonable prices, especially in countries where higher education fees are high, and the courses and degrees offered in this context have increased the percentage of people who prefer micro-credit over the years, as shown in the numbers given by Class-Central.

The Rise of Micro-credentials

Increasingly rapid advances in technology and the labour market require graduates and professionals in the workforce to be familiar with state-of-the-art knowledge, and to possess the skills and competences needed to make full use of technological and non-technological know-how. Content-laden degrees are not always effective for adult learners in today's fast paced environment and employees also need 'just-in-time' skills development that is immediately applicable (Debiais-Sainton, 2020).

According to European Commission (2021) a micro-credential is the record of the learning outcomes that a learner has acquired following a small volume of learning. These learning outcomes have been assessed against transparent and clearly defined standards. These learner-centered new pathways of learning have been quite popular as they offer portable, stackable, and recognised learning credits to learners. Upon completing a micro-credential course, learners get certificates or badges that certify their completion of the course and skill acquisition. It's just the same for most of the major games; there is an accompanying set of achievements, or badges. Every time a player achieves a particular task (kill 50 zombies without reloading, drive over every tree in the enchanted forest, smash every Lego fire hydrant, etc.) they get a small digital badge on their big page of achievements. Micro-credentials take a similar approach to education (Greene, 2019). The micro-credentials landscape can be a means of accentuating assessment and validation processes by providing badges and certificates. In different sectors, this could include credit and non-credit-bearing competency development. For the most part, micro-credentials exist outside the formal qualifications frameworks of traditional universities and colleges, yet these frameworks provide formal guidance, because learners will want micro-credentials to be transparent and applicable to formal credentials (McGreal and Olcott, 2022).

Transparent, stackable and portable micro-credentials create a more flexible learning environment for learners. They can store, collect and share their certificates they acquire from micro-credentials via their digital wallets like Europass or Blockcerts. One of the domains suitable for adopting blockchain technology is the micro-credentials domain, where the key advantages of blockchain technology like immutability, time stamp, redundancy, anonymity and its decentralised nature can be a solution to store, collect and share these certificates and badges.

The Pros and Cons of Using Blockchain Technologies for Micro-credentials

The digital conveniences that blockchain technology will provide for the sharing, storage and stacking of the skills and competencies acquired in the fields of education and business have been seen with applications that will help individuals acquire the acquired skills easily in the national and international context, and that the lessons taken with micro-credits can be experienced by the wider masses. The benefits of blockchain technology for micro-credited learning environments are grouped under 3 main headings in the report titled "Building the Credential Infrastructure of the Future" prepared by the board led by MIT University (Duffy et al., 2020). These titles are:

- **Multiple Redundancy:** Decentralized systems such as blockchain allow recording at multiple points, unlike the systems managed from a single center. The risk of system crash in records obtained from a single center may put individuals in a difficult situation in accessing the records.
- **Immutability:** It is very difficult to change or remove educational data structured with blockchain technology. This is because any update made on the blockchain is visible to all stakeholders.
- **Timestamp:** A reliable timestamp is essential for checking the validity of the micro-credit. Each added blockchain data is marked with a timestamp.

Apart from these benefits, blockchain technology has some anticipated risks. Excessive use of blockchain technologies for micro-credentials can endanger student privacy, furthermore, individuals' right to be forgotten is compromised by blockchain technology, which is close to impossible to delete or change data. The high

computer power required for the operation of the blockchain brings high energy use and carbon emissions, which points to high carbon emissions, which is one of the main criticisms of blockchain technologies. Considering the possible harm it will cause to the nature with high carbon emissions, considering the high number of students in the world, blockchain technology should be transformed in an operable way with less energy use.

Apart from the possible damage to user privacy and nature, another negative side of using blockchain technology in both micro-lending and other online learning activities will be the scalability problem, especially in the case of slow-speed blockchain technologies (Alammary et al., 2019). At this point, the problem requires the verification of all stakeholders in the block while many data belonging to a student are stored, while as the number of students in question increases, this verification will slow down and cause problems as the scale grows. Optimization of registry areas and therefore blockchain technologies has been proposed to solve these problems (Bruce, 2014).

Blockchain Technology and DALE (Decentralized Autonomous Learning Environments)

Cryptocurrencies are based on blockchain technology. Simply, blockchain store the data in blocks which are interrelated. This innovative technology makes it easy to verify the authenticity of data. The decentralized nature of this technology makes it innovative for future management solutions.

In the world's leading higher education institutions, digital certificate systems based on microcredit have started to be built on blockchain technology. One of the best examples of this is the Blockcerts Universal Verifier system developed by MIT. The underlying blockchains powering digital certificates write their cryptographically supported proof on an immutable ledger transparently to all parties, making them a real and verifiable authority.

The unique fit between microcredit and blockchain systems has rapidly increased the relevant research in the literature. Wu (2022) explored the blockchain backed digital credentialing for a decentralized micro-credentials ecosystem. A system for building and deploying permanent, counterfeit-resistant competency level micro-credentials have been described. The thesis found that a blockchain micro-credential certifications system powered by smart contracts could be built after addressing smart contract design and user interface design challenges. In another dissertation, Erbguth (2022) suggest a framework for long-term revocable credentials. The proposed solution is an open solution that can be adopted by different institutions. They can do this by sharing a smart contract and can provide the possibility of cross-verification of credentials with a minimal decentralized governance structure as being found.

DAO (decentralized autonomous organization) is a relatively new blockchain acronym that aims to decentralize the management of organizations with help of smart contracts. The smart contract is the backbone technology of the DAOs. The contract identifies and manage the rules of the organization. These technologies provide an autonomous and open vision in the management of organizations.

Like the DAOs, ODL (open and distance learning) have an open nature. The openness philosophy of ODL make it convenient for blockchain technologies. The ultimate goal of almost all ODL future scenarios is to achieve an open, in-life, seamless, united ecosystem. To build such a united ecosystem, all stakeholders of ODL need more flexible, transferable, scalable systems. Macroprudential well deserve to be the solution for these needs. However, micro credentials require a very fast verification technology which can be tracked and verified all around the world. All these features refer to blockchain technology and DAOs. We believe that the nature of DAO technologies will be the backbone of this vision. To achive this vision, we propose a system named DALE (Decentralized Autonomous Learning Ecosystem).

DALE

Decentralized Autonomous Learning Ecosystem

Figure 1. Layers of DALE

Dale consists of 4 layers built on the Core. Each layer is built on the blocks of the previous one. This layer also serves as a source for creating the blocks of the next layer. The Core, like the cell nucleus, is at the center of the DALE ecosystem. Core hosts DAO technologies and blockchain technologies. Core, contains the core codes of the ecosystem. Core managed by DAO technology with support of native Pi network. Administrative decisions in DALE are voted by crypto-asset holders.

Level 1 is dedicated to Nodes of the ecosystem. Nodes are Educational Providers in the system. Educational Provider can be University, School, Lab or even individual. Each node supports the DALE network. Nodes supports the DALE through validation and relaying transactions. Nodes have a copy of the full blockchain. Technically, nodes are the servers of the providers. Level 2 host micro-credits of the DALE. Credits generated by Providers(Nodes) in accordance with DALE Accreditation Standards. DALE-AS contains metrics and metadata standarts for Credits. DALE Accreditation Standards works on Blockcerts Open Standard for Blockchain Certificates. Level 3 is made up of LOs (Learning Objects). LOs are integrated, transferable learning units. LO is a collection of content items, practice items, and assessment items. These components are combined on learning objectives. LOs represent the courses in DALE. Each LO is connected with credits. Level 4 is the front-end of the DALE. Level 4 contains Smart Contents. Smart Contents are produced based on and integrated with LOs. AI technologies makethe produced contents smart. A sensitive and personalized learning interface is provided in DALE. This interface managed by AI models and Learning Analytics. Thus, a sensitive learning interface powered by learner experiences is presented.

In the ecosystem, there are 5 categories of work areas: 1) content production, 2) instructional design and quality, 3) material production, 4) mining for local cryptoassets, 5) mentoring. Each area has defined work packages, producing cells and teams. Jobs in the first two categories are more preferred by field experts, instructional designers, and educational technologists. The remaining categories are open to everyone. As long as it complies with versatile control standards. Learners are more active in Guidance category. They can work by guiding others on a subject which they have learned well (proven profile point). All payments are paid in local cryptocurrency. Looking at the business model, DALE is a self-build, evolutionarily developing system.

Conclusions

In this study, the decentralized common structure of micro-credentials and blockchain technologies are discussed. Both micro-credentials and blockchain are structures that have gained popularity in the last 10 years. The rise of micro-credentials and blockchain technologies point to a wide paradigm shift at the same time. Both systems have a structure that focuses on decentralization and emphasizes creativity and flexibility by combining blocks. This natural harmony also highlights the idea of building micro-credentials on blockchain technologies. Especially DAO structures can make important contributions to the management of microcredits.

A microcredit built on blockchain requires innovative education systems. It is very difficult for traditional educational institutions to integrate into such a structure. Open and Distance Learning systems can be considered as the most suitable structures for such an integration. From this point of view, the DALE model, which is compatible with ODL systems and makes use of micro-credentials and blockchain, has been proposed. DALE represents an open learning ecosystem on the network. DALE participants are not limited to educational institutions. In future studies, the layered structure of the DALE model can be designed and developed, and the application infrastructure can be evaluated with its advantages and limitations.

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